

Smooth Transition Maps

Ryan J. Buchanan

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Abstract

A transition map $f : a \rightarrow b$ is a differential tool for allowing one to switch between local frames of reference. We give some information about this tool here.

1 Background

A transition map (of coordinate charts) $f : a \rightarrow b \cong f : \phi_\alpha \circ \phi_\beta^{-1}$, is essentially a functor between two categories \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} , which consists of neighborhoods as objects and paths between neighborhoods as the morphisms. However, the idea of smoothness (in a geometric sense) only makes sense if we have some notion of differentiation; that is, we must be able to differentiate morphisms in both \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} up to infinity. For every $a \in \mathcal{A}$ and for every $b \in \mathcal{B}$, there is a neighborhood $\mathcal{U}(a \vee b)$, a boundary $\partial_i(a \vee b)$, and a coboundary $\partial^i(a \vee b)$. We can take commutative and associative compositions of unions and intersections to form a G_δ space, where G is a group and δ is a “closeness” relationship. I.e., if $a\delta a'$, then a and a' are said to be proximal to one another, or to be in proximity with each other.

This is to say, we can reach a' from a by a vector whose norm is εp , for some prime p , and some sufficiently small ε . The notion of smallness here is slightly non-trivial. By “sufficiently small,” we mean that $\delta_i(\varepsilon)$ exists only as a subobject, but never as an object; i.e., we can never take the one-object category of ε , and therefore maps to and from this value are not functors. Therefore, $\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \delta_i(k) = \varepsilon$. The existence of this quantity then, both depends upon, and ensures the proper smoothness of its geometric representation.

In the past, I have used the concept of Ricci iteration:

$$Ric_{g_{i+1}}(x) = x_t \rightarrow x_{t+1} \tag{1.1}$$

as a discrete time-step operator. However, we can replace it by:

$$Ric_{g_{i+\varepsilon}} = x_t \rightarrow x_{t+\varepsilon} \tag{1.2}$$

when our category is *Vect*-enriched, with a C^∞ animation. This was expanded upon greatly by Florés [1], who provided an interpretation of this iteration in bra-ket notation.

To summarize, the Ricci iteration is a way of providing an infinitesimal derivative, or as Islam might call them, a *proper Newtonian fluxion*. They are geometric in nature, as opposed to topological or algebraic, and represent the information one could theoretically obtain in an ideal time-series analysis.

There is an isomorphism of maps:

$$\delta_{i+1}(\bullet) \cong \{Rig_{g_{i+\varepsilon}} | \varepsilon \mapsto \varepsilon^{i+1}\} \quad (1.3)$$

This actually has a tantalizingly suggestive motivation: it implies that, as more measurements are made by the same observer, increasingly minute and subtle detail are observed. This naturally gives rise to the quantum Zeno effect. As we iterate over (differentiate with respect to) time, we obtain closer and closer measurements the finer the interval of time that is used.

The statement:

$$\exists \mathfrak{t} \quad (1.4)$$

where $\mathfrak{t} : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathcal{B}$ is a smooth transition, is essentially akin to granting the practicing observer an infinite amount of information.

Proposition 1.1. $\exists \mathfrak{t} \iff \mathcal{C}^\infty(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}) \implies \mathcal{A} \& \mathcal{B} \text{ are Lipschitz}$

and all of the above imply the existence of an infinite number of neighborhoods, as well as the existence of $\partial^\infty(a \vee b)$ and $\partial_\infty(a \vee b)$. The cardinality of the set of paths is $Card(Aut(\mathbb{1}_\infty)) = Card(Hom([0, 1], Id_{[0, 1]}))$.

2 Locality and Reference

A smooth transition map is a way of transporting an observer from a frame of reference $LocSys(\mathcal{A})$ to $LocSys(\mathcal{B})$. These are pure gauge bundles which are inherently physical.¹

Definition 2.1. Let X be decomposable as $T_v X$ and $T_h X$. A gauge bundle, $Bun_G(X, \Gamma)$, consists of X , along with a compatible collection of sections Γ (compatible with any metric on X) such that every fiber $\gamma_i \in \Gamma$ has a vertical and horizontal component.

Imagine we have a particle $p = \int_0^i p_i dp$ travelling along the surface of a smooth manifold $\mathcal{M} \cong \mathbb{R}^n$. To every intersection $p \cap \gamma_i$, we have a unique stalk of a sheaf giving the desired values about the particle; for instance, temperature, charge, mass, spin, etc. In the finite k case of $C^k(\mathcal{M})$, all of these variables are discrete; however, in the smooth case, some are not. Call the set of all desired values \mathcal{S} . Then, we have a map: $C^{k \rightarrow \infty}(\mathcal{M}) = \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathcal{S} \times \mathbb{1}_\infty$.

2.1 Prolongation

Let $X \rightarrow E$ be a smooth map and $\Gamma : X \xrightarrow{\infty} E$ a collection of sections: $\Gamma = \sum \bigcup_{i=1}^{\aleph_1} \gamma_i$. Let $*_p$ be a potential location for a point-particle. Then, the *prolongation* of Γ is given by:

$$\Gamma_{Prol} = \langle \langle \int_{\mathbb{C}} (\gamma_i \cap *_p) di \rangle \rangle \quad (2.1)$$

where by $\langle \langle \bullet \rangle \rangle$, we mean the Taylor expansion of \bullet . So, the prolongation is then the integral of Taylor expansions of sections at p .

¹Hancock and I once had a discussion about the difference between a coordinate chart and a frame-of-reference. We came to the conclusion that coordinate charts were purely mathematical, while FoRs were purely physical.

Theorem 2.1. *There is an isomorphism*

$$(LocSys(\mathcal{A}) \leftrightarrow LocSys(\mathcal{B})) \cong (\Gamma_{Prol} \rightarrow \Gamma'_{Prol})$$

Proof. Let $\mathcal{O}_{[\mathcal{A}]}$ be a sheaf of reference frames. Then, we define an equivalence relationship $\overset{g}{\sim}$ such that, for a section γ_i and a stalk $s_t \in \mathcal{O}_{[\mathcal{A}]}$, we have $\gamma_i \overset{g}{\sim} s_t$, which is associative, reflexive, symmetric, and commutative. Call this “gerbe equivalence.”

Then, for \mathcal{S} lying over $*_p$, we have that there is a smooth transformation $\mathcal{C}^{k \rightarrow \infty}(\mathcal{M})$ of the manifold on which the frames are defined. \square

Remark 2.1. *This proof relies on the inclusion $\iota^*([\mathcal{A}])$ as defined in section 1. This ensures that we are working with a “classical” manifold (i.e., smooth, Hausdorff, and second countable).*

A References

- [1] L.R. Florés, *Gravitational Mechanics and Time*, (Unfinished draft)
- [2] P. Emmerson, *Proétale*, (2023)
- [3] R.J. Buchanan, *Some remarks on the generalization of atlases*, (2023)
- [4] R.J. Buchanan, P. Emmerson, *Scattering of Worldlines Along a Bordism*, (2023)